

Factors Affecting Dropout Rate at Secondary School Level in Private Schools of Punjab, Pakistan

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was aimed at assessment of the contribution of private School management to increase enrollment and retention rate at secondary school level at private schools in Punjab. A major objective of the study was to highlight the reason of dropout. A sample of 93(31 head teacher and 62 Secondary school teacher) were selected systematically from private schools of Punjab. 2 separate questionnaires for school heads and class teachers were prepared and administered personally among the respondent. Collected data was analyzed by considering the objectives of the study. The descriptive statistics tools were used to analyze including percentage and mean score. It appears from the data that majority of respondents were of the view that many of the students change their school due to the quality of education, frequent change of teacher, physical facilities and nonqualified staff. It was further assessed that poverty and unemployment is a reason of dropout at the secondary school level. Majority of respondents were of the view that corporal punishment and uneducated parents cause a dropout. It was recommended that to increase school enrollment school should organize parents teacher meeting and should provide a learning environment. School should offer some scholarship and some technical courses to overcome unemployment and poverty issues

Keywords: Dropout Rate, Secondary School Level, Private Schools Punjab

INTRODUCTION

A school is a place where a child starts its professional learning. In Pakistan, there are three types of schools working Public Schools, Private Schools, and Public-Private Partnership Schools.

Public Schools are those schools which are totally funded and managed by Government either provisional or national. In these schools, students do not pay a fee. The government also provides free of cost books to students. So students are free from financial burden, whereas private schools are those schools which are administrated by individuals or private organizations. These schools generate their funds from charging tuition fees from their students. The third type of schools is managed and funded by both government and individuals. These types of schools are normally managed by provisional government in Pakistan. A large number of students get enrolled in private schools. When a child enters in a school for learning the purpose, he is properly enrolled in that school. To retain that student in the school to complete his education is called retention. Every Private School wants to retain his students up to completion of their study. The private school has the focus to increase their enrollment and retention rate. School Management System tries to increase student's enrollment and retention. Management is a core function of any organization, without proper management a system cannot sustain for a long time. Basic functions of management are planning, organizing, controlling and leading.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

“Management is one of most important science which is necessary for effectiveness in producing all kind of goods and services for better output” (Fayyaz, 2007)

According to (Stoner, J.A.Freeman, & Gilbert, 2000) management is a key factor for the success of any organized activity and is an essential accompaniment to all social organization. Management is discipline and culture. It is the life of giving and dynamic organ of any institution it manages. Today management refers to managing changes and challenges, crises, complexities, confidence, culture and credibility.

“A teacher's role involves more than simply standing in front of a classroom and lecturing. In fact, even though a teacher spends the majority of the day in the classroom, the actual teaching component is only part of the job. An effective teacher understands that teaching involves wearing multiple hats to ensure that the school day runs smoothly and all students receive a quality education.”(Zeiger, 2014)

“School management has two aspects- internal management and external management. Internal management covers admission, management of the library, laboratory, building and other physical and

material resources of the school. External management covers the relations with community, department and other person and agencies connected with establishment and functioning of the school.” (M. Dash, 2008) In most country educational management is considered very important. It is the key element of any nation’s success because language is the main thing in it. Every country has their native language and most people who live in their country can’t even what is their native language is. So, it is up to the educational management to help their people learn by making their schools and other education departments system better.

2.1 ENROLLMENT

An enrollment program detects that how much students are being registered in any education whether it is a school or college it is must for everyone to see that how many times a person has attended his class or lecture. Because enrollment indicates that how well and famous an education department is going. These days the only best way to have a great education system is first to make their enrollment system perfect.

According to (Wayland, 1850)“Our Colleges are not filled because we do not furnish the education desired by the people. We have produced an article for which demand is diminishing. We sell it at less than cost, and the deficiency is made up by charity. We give it away, and the demand still diminishes.”

In order to make a perfect school and college according to their educational management, it is very important that you first make a great enrollment system where your institute gets praised about its way of teachings and great education management. You can’t simply open any education organization in your area unless there are many students who want to get educated.

2.2 RETENTION

Nowadays, the education system of schools is getting very bad because of using violence and bullying this is the main reason why most enrollments of the students in the schools are getting lower day by day, where people mostly come here to get an education on their favorite subjects. Schools once were referred as the only organization to make your growth not only on education level but as a human being as well. Because schools are very big where most students are adults and can do anything they want. But what are the reasons that from schools the enrollment and retention are disappearing?

There can be much effective enrollment and retention management programs, but each one is different from others because of culture and population of students. Enrollment management has become a business today many corporations are working as an advisory council for enrollment management. (Dennis, 1998)

2.3 Basic Premises Regarding Enrollment & Retention

1. There can be no successful enrollment management program without a successful retention management program.
2. Without Faculty involvement no enrollment management program can be run
3. An enrollment management program can market only what a school is going to offer or has offered.
4. Financial Aid Program of school will surely affect the enrollment management and retention program.
5. Retention management and enrollment should have focused on goals
6. There is no authentic formula that describes that why students leave school or why they enroll in school.
7. Duration of three years is mandatory required to implement a program of enrollment management and retention management successfully.
8. Any program of retention management or enrollment management can only be successful if it is according to the culture of the school.
9. It is not one man show it is the responsibility of all management, staff, and faculty to run a successful program.
10. There is a lot of magic to this. If we treat students well, if we make them feel that they are our educational partner, they will surely come to our school. (Dennis, 1998)

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This study had a concern with private schools that deals SSC. In every private school number of students in lower classes is higher than SSC classes. Enrollment rate at SSC classes is lower than primary classes. The dropout rate at SSC classes is much higher, and retention rate is lower. After completing their elementary education students either shift to public sector schools or leave the education without completing SSC. Therefore it is crucial to study the dynamics affecting retention and enrollment trends in school management aspects

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study was to highlight the reasons for drop out at secondary school level in private school.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

1. What are the reasons of dropout at the secondary level in private schools?
2. Can a principal lessen dropout rate at secondary school level?

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

1. This study will help the head teachers in planning.
2. This study will assist the policymaker to formulate policy.
3. This study will have benefit for principals of private schools.
4. This study will be helpful to ensure quality education.

POPULATION

1. All Private Secondary Schools of Punjab
2. All Principals of Private Secondary Schools of Punjab
3. All teachers of SSC level in private secondary schools of Punjab.

SAMPLE

A sample of 93 (31 Principal of Private Schools and 62 Secondary School Teachers) of Private Schools were selected randomly.

METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURE OF STUDY

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research study was descriptive in nature. The main purpose of the study was to explore the reasons of dropout at secondary school level in Punjab, Pakistan. According to (Shabana Chudary,2011) "Descriptive research is a type of quantitative research that involve making careful descriptions of educational phenomena. Descriptive studies are concerned primarily with determining what exists."

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population of the phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when/why the characteristics occurred. Rather it addresses the "what" question.

INSTRUMENTS OF THE STUDY

Two questionnaires were administered to collect data separately from principals and class teachers.

PREPARATION OF QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaires were self- developed on the basis of objectives and review of related literature of the study.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected through questionnaire personally administered to ensure 100% rate of the respondent.

DATA ANALYSIS

After collection of data, it was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted by calculating the percentage. For each item in the questionnaire, a table was developed for analysis of respondents. Responses for each category recorded on a five-point scale, detail of this scale is as under.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In this chapter data collected through questionnaires was organized, tabulated and interpreted. The basic purpose of the study was to identify the factors affecting dropout rate in private school at the secondary school level. All the principals and Secondary school teachers were involved in the study. Two questionnaires one for Principals of secondary schools and other for Secondary school teachers of secondary schools were developed for collection of data. Data was represented in term of percentage and mean score. The data analyzed is presented in this chapter in the form of tables. Further tabulation has been divided into following two parts. The detail of each part is given as under.

1. Analysis of open Ended Question from Principals of Private Secondary School

Table 1.1: *Analysis of Opinions on State reasons of dropout at secondary school level in your school*

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Injustice with students	24	77.4
Corporal Punishment	28	90.32
Uneducated Parents	19	61.29
Unemployment	30	96.77
Poverty	31	100
Learning Environment	21	67.74
Child labor	17	54.83
Abroad Culture	11	35.48

It shows from the aforementioned data in Table 1.1 that majority of respondents were of the view that injustice with students is a reason of dropout at the secondary school level. The class teacher does not do justice in their class some students are being preferred so other fell complex and leave school. Many of the respondents were of the view that corporal punishment, uneducated parents, unemployment, poverty, learning environment, child labor and abroad culture are reasons of dropout at the secondary school level. People of Pakistan are normally educated

Table 1.2: *Analysis of Opinions on Statement that what role school management can play to control dropout at the secondary level in your school?*

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Parents Workshop	25	80.64
Community Links	29	93.54
Parents Teacher Meetings	21	67.74
Discount in fee	9	29.03
Offer Scholarships	7	22.58

It is indicated in the aforesaid data in Table 1.2 that majority of respondents were of the view that parents' awareness session, community links, parents teacher meeting, discount in fee and offering scholarships can control dropout rate.

2. Analysis of open Ended Question from Teachers of Private Secondary School

Table 2.1: *Analysis of Opinions on State reasons of dropout at secondary school level in your school*

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Corporal Punishment	56	90.3
Uneducated Parents	21	33.9
Unemployment	54	87
Poverty	58	93.5
Learning Environment	31	50
Child labor	19	30.6

It is evident from the aforementioned data in Table 2.1 that majority of respondents were of the view that corporal punishment, uneducated parents, unemployment, poverty, learning environment and child labor are reasons of dropout.

Table 2.2: *Analysis of Opinions on Statement that what role school management can play to control dropout at the secondary level in your school?*

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Parents Workshop	51	82.3
Community Links	60	96.7
Parents Teacher Meetings	58	93.5

It shows in the aforementioned data in Table 2.2 that majority of respondents were of the view that parents' awareness session, community links, parents teacher meeting, can control dropout rate.

Discussion

The research study is an investigation to find out the reasons for dropout at secondary school level in private sector. The purpose of the study was to find out the factor affecting enrollment and retention at secondary school level in private schools. Two questionnaires were developed to collect data from teachers and Principals. The questionnaires consisted of open-ended questions. The results emerged from the analysis of data are discussed under the objective of study as under:

Objective 1: To highlight the reasons for drop out at secondary school level in private school.

Unemployment is also a major reason of dropouts because people think that after investing there several years and money in education they will not be able to get any job in Pakistan they will have to travel abroad, so they take the decision to go abroad in time.

Poverty is one another factor that affects enrollment at secondary school level in Private sector as private schools are charging a high fee which is not payable by everyone.

Both principal and teachers were of the view that corporal punishment, uneducated parents, and conducive learning environment are major reasons of dropout at secondary school level in private schools.

FINDINGS

On the basis of data analysis, following findings were made:

Finding related to open-ended questions of the questionnaire from Principals

These findings based on a recommendation by principals in the open ended Questions

1. Majority of respondents were of the view that corporal punishment is the reason of dropout at the secondary school level.
2. Majority of head teachers revealed that unemployment is a reason of dropout at the secondary school level.
3. Most of the respondents were of the view that conducive learning environment can increase retention rate.
4. All of the respondents were of the view that community links can increase enrollment.
5. Majority of respondents were of the view that co-curricular activities in school can increase retention rate.

Finding related to open-ended questions of the questionnaire from Teachers

These findings based on a recommendation by teachers in the open ended questions.

1. Majority of the respondents were of the opinion that injustice with students is a reason of dropout at the secondary school level.
2. Majority of the respondents were of the view that teachers' satisfaction increase enrollment.
3. Many of the respondents were of the view that character building activities increase retention rate.
4. Most of the respondents were of the view that uneducated parents are the reason of dropout.

CONCLUSIONS

Following conclusions were drawn from the study:

1. Most schools had satisfactory enrollment at the elementary level. However, the enrollment at the secondary level is low.
2. It was concluded that many of students quit their study before completing SSC. Many of the students change their schools due to the poor quality of education. High fee schedule also a reason of dropout at private secondary school.
3. It was concluded that in private school teachers frequently change that cause dropout at the secondary school level. However qualified staff can cause an increase in enrollment
4. It was also concluded that shortage of physical facility cause dropout at the secondary school level.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In order to increase enrollment at secondary school level schools should be produced conducive learning environment. For producing conducive learning, environment school should arrange workshops for teachers time to time and management training for management of the school.
2. In order to increase retention rate at private secondary schools school should establish strong community links. School should organize parents' teacher meetings; establish parents' council and different activities for social involvement.
3. To overcome the reason of poverty or high fee schedule school should plan some scholarship for brilliant students.
4. School should start some technical courses to overcome the problem of unemployment.
5. Teachers should be trained to deal with students affectionately, and corporal punishment should be banned in school.

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